

ON THE CONCEPT OF CREATING INTELLIGENT INFORMATION SECURITY SYSTEMS BASED ON NEURAL NETWORK INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEMS

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Abstract. The subject of research is the concept of creating intelligent information security systems based on neural network intrusion detection systems (IDS) in cyberspace. In research, flexibility, learning, and controllability are considered key conceptual requirements for an IDS system. Special attention is paid to the construction of a flexible intelligent information security system, including IDS, both in the nodes of the system components and in the data transmission networks between the components. Methodological research on the selected research area can be carried out using artificial intelligence, systematic analysis methods and the theory of intelligent information systems in the field of artificial intelligence. The research uses the achievements of the systematic-conceptual approach to information protection in the system. The main result of the research is that the successful protection of information in the system can be implemented only in the form of interconnected local systems using neural network technologies integrated into a single center based on a systematic-conceptual approach. The need to use a single systematic approach based on uniform legal, organizational and technical measures for information protection is based on the need to combat unauthorized attacks. It is considered that the application of a systematic-conceptual approach to the creation of IDS based on neural network technologies will help to develop new tools, methods and measures for the intelligent management of information security in the system.

Keywords: intelligent systems, information security, neural systems, intrusion detection systems, information security strategies, attack detection system

Introduction. An intrusion detection system (IDS) or attack detection system (ADS) is a software or hardware information security tool designed to prevent unauthorized access to systems for various purposes [2]. Intrusion detection systems provide an additional level of information protection[1-10] in

system and are one of the main components of the information security system (Fig. 1).

IDSs built on the basis of neural network technologies[11-26], which are capable of analyzing large data[27-33] flows from the network for the presence of threats and detecting them, are considered promising.

Figure 1. Survey of intrusion detection systems: techniques, datasets and challenges[1]

The peculiarity of artificial neural networks is that these networks can be trained, and after training they are able to adapt to new types of threats and recognize them, even if they have not encountered them before.

Main part:

Software-as-a-service (SaaS) is a license to access a specific cloud application over the Internet. However, these services are delayed and sometimes completely interrupted due to the unavailability of the Internet, which provides opportunities for many attacks. Research on cloud security mainly focuses on preventing malicious users from using the cloud to launch attacks, such as those currently carried out by botnets, including launching DDoS attacks, sending spam, etc. Because SaaS uses computing power from both cloud servers. Computing providers and customers' machines, [2] noted that SaaS can be used in an unprecedented way as an attack vector for botnets (Fig. 2). The term "intrusion" itself, due to its ambiguity, is interpreted differently by security specialists - security breach, attack, penetration, assault, etc. Based on the standard terminology [2], an attack on an information system should be understood as one or more information security incidents associated with the human factor, which together can lead to the implementation of threats by exploiting the vulnerabilities of this information system. An information security

incident is any unexpected or unwanted event that may disrupt business or information security.

Figure 2. A machine learning based attack detection and mitigation using a secure SaaS framework[2]

The concept of creating intelligent information security systems based on neural network attack detection systems in cyberspace can be attributed to the concept of creating systems for critical technologies[1]. The basis of the concept is the construction of a flexible IDS system in nodes of computer networks and in data transmission networks between network nodes. Since IDS components built on neural network technologies, and later with the addition of artificial immune system mechanisms, are functionally independent and trainable subsystems of information security systems in all structural components of the system, the coordination of their work requires the creation of a main control center for these systems[1]. The main conceptual requirements for the IDS system are adaptability and learnability.

Adaptability is achieved by the basic characteristics required of neural systems, and controllability is achieved by regulated processes for implementing macro-processes of information security management.

Intrusion protection functions. The functional approach to the development of IDS is that the concept of information security function is taken as the basis for organizing security, the conceptual requirement for which is the requirement of completeness. The protection function is understood as a functionally homogeneous set of measures and decisions carried out in the interests of ensuring security [8]. The completeness of a function is understood

as their property, which consists in the fact that the systematic and regular implementation of these functions helps to achieve the required level of information security.

Let us formulate a complete set of functions of protection against intrusions in the system: 1) prevention of conditions that give rise to the penetration of intrusions into the system; 2) preventing the penetration of malicious code into the network; 3) detection of emerging intrusions; 4) preventing the impact of intrusion on information; 5) detecting the impact of intrusion on information; 6) localization of the impact of intrusion on information; 7) liquidation of the consequences of the invasion. Depending on the outcome of the implementation of each of the intrusion protection functions, one event will take place out of many resulting events for detection, prevention of impacts, localization and elimination of the consequences of an intrusion, which together constitute a complete set of incompatible random events. It follows that the sum of the probabilities of favorable outcome events expresses the probability of reliable protection of information from intrusions. This creates objective prerequisites for the optimal use of resources allocated to protect information from unauthorized intrusions.

Conclusion

The problem of reliable information security with the help of IDS based on neural network attack detection systems with the use of early and proactive tactics of using effective means, methods and measures of information protection in cyberspace was researched, arising from the general fundamental rules of the systematic-conceptual approach to information protection.

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